

Workshop CIS – AIQUA

CORRELAZIONI MARINO–CONTINENTALI: SVILUPPI E PROSPETTIVE NELLA STRATIGRAFIA E NELLA CARTOGRAFIA DEL QUATERNARIO

Evento inserito nel quadro delle attività scientifiche promosse congiuntamente da COMMISSIONE ITALIANA DI STRATIGRAFIA e ASSOCIAZIONE ITALIANA PER LO STUDIO DEL QUATERNARIO per favorire l'integrazione tra le comunità di ricerca che operano sugli archivi quaternari.

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POSTER ABSTRACTS

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Marine and terrestrial proxies across the Neogene-Quaternary boundary in the central Mediterranean (Sicily)

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This study presents a high-resolution multiproxy climatostratigraphic reconstruction across the Neogene-Quaternary boundary within the Mediterranean Sea. The Global boundary Stratotype Section and Point (GSSP) for the Gelasian Stage (2.588 Ma) ratified in 1996 in the Monte San Nicola type-section (MSNt-s) in Sicily, formally defines the base of the Pleistocene Series and Quaternary System. The studied interval (~2.7-2.5 Ma) falls within a global-scale transition in the climate system recording a progressive long-term cooling linked to the intensification of Northern Hemisphere Glaciation (iNHG).

Within the SQS-ICS-GELSTRAT project, we investigated the MSNt-s which has been significantly enhanced through the acquisition of new high-resolution, multidisciplinary data based on oxygen isotopes, alkenones, calcareous plankton, and pollen assemblages. These data provide multiple evidence of the continuity of the stratigraphic record and a robust chronological framework based on the astronomical tuning of six sapropels (cluster A) to insolation maxima. Their location has been determined integrating field, biogeochemical, and mineralogical analyses.

Our results define a detailed climatostratigraphic framework spanning Marine Isotope Stages (MIS) G4 to the onset of MIS 99. The record documents rapid modifications in upper water column dynamics driven by the complex non-linear feedback mechanisms between the African monsoon and North Atlantic climate systems. During MIS 104, just below the GSSP, our marine proxies captured the southward migration of the Subarctic Front during glacials in agreement with North Atlantic records. Above the GSSP, pollen assemblages detected a significant expansion of colder and dryer conditions on land, documenting increasingly severe glacial-interglacial cycles. Our findings demonstrate that paleoclimate and stratigraphic signals are very well preserved in the type-section the MSNt-s which is continuous, well constrained, and suitable for global correlation.

Quaternary composite marine terraces of southern Sardinia: stratigraphic evidence for variable uplift and terrace reoccupation

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Quaternary marine terraces provide key archives for reconstructing the interplay between sea-level change and tectonics along active coastal margins. However, distinguishing the effects of eustatic forcing from spatially variable uplift remains challenging.

This study investigates Middle–Late Pleistocene sedimentary sequences at three sites along the southern Sardinia coast. Three unconformity-bounded units, correlated with MIS7, MIS5e, and MIS5c highstands, record repeated phases of marine transgression, shallow-marine progradation, and regression. The study areas exhibit contrasting stacking patterns, including composite marine terraces composed of superposed shallow marine highstand deposits separated by erosional surfaces, as well as single marine terrace units.

The elevations of MIS7 and MIS5c deposits relative to present sea level differ from global eustatic benchmarks by up to 15–20 m, a discrepancy that cannot be explained solely by glacio-eustatic fluctuations or Mediterranean glacio-isostatic adjustment. Instead, the data indicate dominant tectonic control. We propose that southern Sardinia is segmented into crustal blocks that have been affected by spatially and temporally variable uplift since at least the Middle–Late Pleistocene, with a possible eastward migration of uplift.

These results show that composite marine terraces represent a key stratigraphic expression of the interaction between tectonics and sea-level fluctuations. Even in regions with relatively low uplift rates, tectonic segmentation can strongly influence coastal stratigraphy, promoting reoccupation processes and the development of composite terrace sequences rather than simple staircase terraces.

Examples of composite marine terraces in the hinterland of the Taranto Gulf (southern Italy)

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The Metaponto area and its hinterland are the youngest exposed part of the south-Appennines foreland-basin facing the Ionian Sea in the Taranto Gulf (southern Italy). It is characterized by the occurrence of narrow middle and late Quaternary terraced marine deposits striking from the chain to the foreland with an along-strike decreasing altitude.

This staircase of depositional terraces, generated by a complex interaction between regional uplift and sea-level changes, is cut by the drainage network of the main rivers of the area that allowed the stratigraphic study of their paralic successions.

These terraced marine deposits record more than a single relative sea-level change in the succession located below each terraced surface, even in the subsurface of the present-day coastal plain; therefore, terraced surfaces topping these deposits could not be genetically linked to the whole succession located below each of these surfaces but, eventually, they could be related to the last of those cycles vertically recorded in the local sedimentary succession that must be often referred to a composite marine terrace.

Some examples of these composite marine terraces were detailed measured and sampled in order to date deposits and try to attribute the surface to the right relative sea-level highstand related to a MIS.

Sedimentary archives in transitional environments: geomorphological and paleoenvironmental evolution of the Val Grande lagoon of Bibione in the Tagliamento delta

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The transitional environments of the north-western Adriatic represent key zones at the interface between marine and continental domains. Their sedimentary successions preserve stratified paleoenvironmental archives capable of recording, with high sensitivity, both marine and terrestrial influences. The Bibione coastal system is one of the most articulated examples in the region, documenting 8000 years of geomorphological evolution driven by sea-level rise, the combined action of marine and fluvial processes, and the increasing impact of human activities. This study integrates high-resolution geomorphological analyses, extensive stratigraphic datasets, historical cartography, and archaeobotanical evidence to reconstruct the evolution of the area from the Middle Holocene to the Early Middle Ages. More than 1300 hand-drilled cores collected between 2022-2024 and six mechanical cores reaching depths of up to 25 m were combined with LiDAR-derived digital elevation models to build a detailed stratigraphic framework of the coastal sector of the Tagliamento River plain. This approach reveals the distribution of alluvial, lagoonal and coastal deposits and clarifies the processes responsible for the formation of the Mutteron dei Frati dune system. These dunes, the highest along the Adriatic coast (up to 11 m), hosted a Roman coastal villa built in the 1st century BCE and occupied until the 5th century CE. The new stratigraphic and geomorphological data allow the reconstruction of a sector of the Roman shoreline, highlighting the recurved termination of the Mutteron dei Frati dunes as a key indicator of a former tidal inlet connecting the lagoon to the open sea. This tidal mouth reached a depth of about 25 m in the 3rd century BCE and preserves an exceptional laminated sequence of fine-grained sediments. Pollen analyses from targeted cores in Val Grande provide evidence of lagoonal environments characterized by halophytic and marsh vegetation, as well as localized anthropogenic signals consistent with the occupation phases of the Roman villa located beside the dune ridge. Combined with radiocarbon chronology, the pollen data also allow precise identification of the Tagliamento River avulsion that affected the Caorle lagoon in the late 6th century CE. Overall, the integration of geomorphological and archaeobotanical data offers a robust reconstruction of coastal dynamics and long-term landscape transformations around the Mutteron dei Frati coastal system of Bibione.

High-resolution climate oscillations across the Piacenzian/Gelasian boundary.

Planktonic foraminifera and stable isotopes from Punta Piccola and Mandorlo (sections (Sicily))

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The Mediterranean is an area of particular interest as it is particularly exposed to natural risks, in terms of desertification, acidification of water masses and loss of biodiversity. The study aims to reconstruct the effects of climatic oscillations on planktonic foraminifera in two key sections (Punta Piccola and Monte S. Nicola) outcropping in southern Sicily where Piacenzian and Gelasian GSSPs were defined.

Punta Piccola and Monte San Nicola sections successions cover the stratigraphic intervals between 3.5 and 1.6 Ma and are astro-bio-magneto-chronologically well calibrated, characterized by beautiful lithological cycles controlled by Milankovitch periodicities. Regards the Monte San Nicola outcrop, the samples have been collected in the succession called “Mandorlo” not far from the Gelasian GSSP, and already studied by various authors. In the present study we compare the obtained data with those published for the GSSP type section and with those of Faro Rossello lighthouse section.

To understand the mechanisms controlling climate variations, a multidisciplinary approach has been used, carrying out quantitative analysis on planktonic foraminifera, stable isotopes ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and alkenones to estimate the paleotemperatures of surface waters, as well as than as a proxy for marine productivity. The study has been focused between MIS G1 and MIS 95. The data shows a progressive temperature decrease, characterized by $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ heavier values marked by increasing in cold species as for instance the polar species *Neogloboquadrina atlantica*. The cooling trend coincides with the disappearance of sapropel layers. The cooling event, which culminates at MIS 100, falls within a phase of obliquity minima reduction and eccentricity minimum. Glacial/interglacial events are well marked by oxygen isotope curve and *Globigerinoides* spp. fluctuations. Spectral analysis highlights a dominance of 41 ky periodicity, linked to obliquity, and in minor way precession/insolation cycles.

Paleoenvironmental variability during formation of the sapropelic Nicola bed (MIS 103, ~2.59 Ma) at Monte San Nicola, Mandorlo section (Sicily)

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A high-resolution multiproxy investigation was carried out across the reddish microlaminated sapropelic Nicola bed (bed A5) exposed at the Mandorlo section, outcropping at Monte San Nicola (near Gela, Sicily), approximately 400 m west of the Gelasian GSSP. The Nicola bed corresponds to i-cycle 250 and is assigned to Marine Isotope Stage (MIS) 103 (2.59 Ma). The Global boundary Stratotype Section and Point (GSSP) for the Pliocene–Pleistocene (Gelasian–Calabrian) boundary is at the base of the marl immediately above the Nicola bed, making this level visually recognizable throughout. This research was conducted within the framework of the GELSTRAT project and the PRIN-PNRR project “ReMePP” involving Palermo and Bari research units. Due to its friable nature, the Nicola bed was consolidated with resin and a single 41-cm-long block (G6) was extracted using a rock saw. Samples were subsequently collected at 1-cm intervals. The applied multiproxy approach includes analyses of planktonic and benthic foraminiferal assemblages, stable isotope measurements on the planktonic foraminifera *Globigerinoides ruber* and *Globigerina bulloides*, and total organic carbon (TOC) determinations. The Nicola bed reaches a thickness of 19.8 cm and displays bioturbation only in its uppermost part, mainly represented by *Trichichnus* and *Chondrites*. Three distinct paleoenvironmental intervals were identified based on foraminiferal assemblages. The lower interval, underlying the Nicola bed, is characterized by diversified benthic communities indicative of well-oxygenated bottom waters. Conversely, within the microlaminated levels, benthic assemblages are strongly depleted as a consequence of dysoxic to anoxic seafloor conditions. In these layers, planktonic foraminifera dominate and the planktonic/benthic ratio reaches 100%. TOC values remain below 0.6%, significantly lower than the conventional 2% threshold commonly used to define sapropelic deposits. Oxygen isotope records show marked fluctuations, with values exceeding 2‰. In particular, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values measured on *G. ruber* range between -3 and 0.2 ‰, suggesting pronounced sea-surface temperature variability and enhanced freshwater input associated with increased runoff.

Geology between land and sea in the low-lying coastal system of Emilia-Romagna (Italy)

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Low-lying sandy coasts are complex depositional systems whose evolution is controlled by the interaction between eustatic variations and subsidence, sediment supply, and coastal processes.

This study presents an integrated geological analysis for the land–sea transition in the Northern Adriatic coastal system (Emilia-Romagna, Italy), aimed at improving knowledge on coastal risk, focusing on the stratigraphic framework and sedimentological characterization of coastal and nearshore deposits. The analysis is based on a multi-source dataset acquired over time by the Emilia-Romagna region and CNR-ISMAR, through dedicated surveys carried out since 2010, which significantly improved the regional database. The dataset includes high-resolution seismic reflection profiles (CHIRP sub-bottom profiler), boreholes, cone penetration tests (CPTU), sediment sampling and laboratory analysis. Geophysical surveys cover the shallow marine sector from ~1–2 m to 8–10 m water depth and are integrated with deeper offshore profiles from existing archives. CPTUs and boreholes, conducted both onshore and offshore, allow direct calibration of seismic facies and reconstruction of subsurface stratigraphy. Laboratory analyses further constrain sediment composition and depositional processes, including grain-size distribution, XRF core scanning for high-resolution elemental variability, magnetic susceptibility measurements, and radiocarbon dating. These data provide key information on sediment provenance, facies variability, and the timing of depositional phases, enabling robust stratigraphic correlations across the coastal system. Results highlight the continuity between continental and marine depositional environments and identify the active beach and shoreface as a laterally persistent sedimentary body forming the uppermost stratigraphic unit. Its internal architecture reflects the balance between erosional and depositional processes driven by wave climate and sediment transport. Stratigraphic reconstruction reveals stacking patterns controlled by relative sea-level changes, subsidence, and sediment supply, documenting Late Quaternary phases of progradation, retrogradation, and coastal reworking. This study demonstrates that the integration of high-resolution geophysical data, direct stratigraphic observations, and laboratory analyses is essential to resolve the architecture of the land–sea transition and to interpret the evolution of low-gradient coastal systems within a coherent geological framework. Such a framework also provides a fundamental basis for coastal risk assessment, allowing a better understanding of the geological controls on shoreline variability, sediment deficits, and the response of coastal systems to sea-level rise and extreme events.

Highstand, drop and stillstand during MIS 5.5: new data from Taranto and Lizzano areas

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Two terraced units and associated paleoshorelines dating back to the Last Interglacial (LIG) have been recognised in the Taranto and Lizzano areas: i) Unit 1 (U1LIG), further subdivided into lower/inner and upper/outer, associated with a paleoshoreline at $+30\pm 2$ m (PS1LIG), and ii) Unit 2 (U2LIG), associated with a paleoshoreline at $+20\pm 2$ m (PS2LIG).

U1LIG-lower/inner, dated between ca. 135 and ca. 128 ka, exhibits stratal geometry, lithofacies distribution, and stratigraphic relationship with the U1LIG-upper/outer unit that together point to the transgression (sea level-rise) toward the first highstand of MIS 5.5.

U1LIG-upper/outer, dated to ca. 127 ka, shows stratal geometry, lithofacies distribution, and stratigraphic relationship with U1LIG-lower/inner, that together identify the MIS 5.5 highstand.

The lower U2LIG unit, which gives a broad chronological range of 127-122 ka, and its associated lower paleoshoreline PS2LIG, record a second, lower sea-level stillstand/slow sea-level lowering during MIS 5.5, occurred after a rapid drop in sea level.

Assuming a constant regional uplift rate and a sea-level within a range of +2 to +9 m at the first and highest MIS 5.5 highstand, we reconstruct, for the study areas, that: i) the first highstand of MIS 5.5 peaked at ca. 127 ka BP; ii) thereafter, an intra-LIG sea-level drop of ca. 9.4 ± 4.1 m occurred; iii) the rapid drop was followed by a second stillstand/slow sea-level lowering (represented by PS2LIG in our study area). The rapid sea-level drop and the following second stillstand/slow sea-level lowering can be assumed in the interval of ca. 127-122 ka. The post-127 ka sea-level fall and the following second stillstand/slow sea-level lowering coincide with the time of deposition of the Sapropel S5. The large amount of eluvial and colluvial material in U2LIG, together with its deltaic facies, are the local signal of the Sapropel S5 event. This implies that, during the deposition period of U2LIG that coincides with the S5 event, southern Italy experienced intensified rainfall. Our data refine and extend previous findings that warm interglacial periods, marked by enhanced freshwater flux by the monsoonal Nile (and wadi-systems) floods, were characterized by increased precipitation in the NW Mediterranean.

Stratigraphic correlations between continental and marine successions cropping out in the Bradano Foredeep Pliocene-Quaternary Basin (Southern Italy)

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The NW-SE-trending Pliocene-Quaternary Bradano Foredeep basin is located between the Apennine chain and the carbonate platform of the Apulian foreland, hosting the area of dispersal of the Mt. Vulture pyroclastic products, southern Italy. Stratigraphic studies conducted in the areas surrounding the villages of Venosa, Pomarico, and Montalbano Ionico revealed the presence of volcanoclastic deposits correlated with the Fara d'Olivo ignimbrite of the Mt. Vulture volcanic succession. Outcrops of the products of Mt. Vulture volcano have been identified within the fluvial-lacustrine volcanoclastic succession of the mid-Pleistocene Venosa Basin, made of the sedimentary infill of a paleovalley (approximately 1.5 km wide and 50 km long) cut in the Pleistocene Bradano foredeep deposits. At the base, the volcanics rest on siliciclastic alluvial conglomerates. In the area surrounding the village of Pomarico, a 27 m-thick fluvio-lacustrine succession overlies the marine regressive succession of the Bradano foredeep. The stratigraphic boundary is marked by a 15 cm-thick palaeosol. The continental succession consists of lacustrine red-brown, fine- to medium-grained silty-clayey sands, with metric intercalations of alluvial pebbly sandstone. The basal coarse-grained alluvial sediments consist of 2 m-thick trough cross-stratified conglomerate, overlain by 4.80 m-thick planar- and trough cross-stratified sandstone with centimetre-sized white pumice concentrated along the layering surfaces. The pumice has been correlated with the Fara d'Olivo ignimbrite eruption of the Mt. Vulture volcano based on geochemical similarities. In the Montalbano area, nine volcanic layers (V1-V9) were identified at different stratigraphic levels within a marine clay succession. The layer labelled V4 ($^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ age 773.9 ± 1.2 ka) was attributed to the Fara d'Olivo ignimbrite, based on geochemical similarities. The presence of Mt. Vulture volcanic tephra enables regional-scale correlations between continental (alluvial and lacustrine) and marine successions within the Bradano foredeep basin. Furthermore, it allows recognizing a basal erosional surface that distinguishes uplifted sectors from subsiding portions of the basin. It can be therefore used in the geological cartography as a regional-scale boundary extending from the Apennine chain to the foredeep basin.

Morpho-sedimentological setting and late Quaternary evolution of the Hafrsfjord Strait (SW Norway) based on hydrodynamic, bathymetric, and seismo-stratigraphic data

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Straits represent critical marine connections between adjacent basins, acting as dynamic conduits for water masses, nutrients, and biota, where active sedimentary processes reshape mobile substrates through erosion, dispersal, and deposition. Despite their scientific relevance, many modern strait systems remain poorly characterized from a geological perspective, particularly regarding systems that developed during the Quaternary-Holocene in glacial or peri-glacial settings, where processes differ from analogous systems located at lower latitudes.

This poster presents a preliminary geological characterization of the Hafrsfjord Strait (H.S.), a multi-segmented coastal entrance connecting an inner embayment with the open Atlantic Ocean in southwestern Norway. The H.S. has been investigated through an integrated, multi-disciplinary methodological approach, combining: (i) hydrodynamic measurements to reconstruct current velocity, direction, water-mass stratification, and overall circulation patterns within the strait; (ii) high-resolution multibeam bathymetric surveying to define the physiography, depth ranges, and seafloor morphology of the system; (iii) sediment sampling and grain-size analysis to characterize lithological variability and assess the interplay between current dynamics and bottom sediment distribution; and (iv) sub-bottom seismic profiling to resolve the stratigraphic architecture of the shallow subsurface (down to -30 m) and reconstruct the sequence of post-glacial depositional events. These methodologies were deployed to address two principal scientific objectives: (i) assessing whether the H.S. conforms to existing depositional models for strait environments, and (ii) reconstructing the geological history of the system over the past $\sim 20,000$ years. The stratigraphic record investigated spans the principal stages of post-glacial evolution, from glacial over-deepening and Younger Dryas morainal deposition, through the Holocene transgression and progressive marine flooding, to the present-day configuration of a tidally influenced threshold fjord.

The Lower Pleistocene transition from shallow marine to coastal and fluvial environments in the Paglia–Tevere Graben (Lazio Region)

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The peri-Tyrrhenian basin of Paglia–Tevere Graben represents an ideal area for studying and mapping the lateral and vertical transition between Lower Pleistocene shallow-marine, coastal, and continental siliciclastic deposits. Its southern sector, located between the carbonate ridges of Monte Soratte and the Sabini Mountains and extending over approximately 100 km², is characterized by numerous well-exposed natural outcrops, including cliffs, abandoned and active quarries, and road cuts. These exposures allow detailed examination of lithofacies and reconstruction of the basin stratigraphic architecture.

The main component of the syn-rift basin fill consists of the high-rank depositional sequence corresponding to the Chiani–Tevere Formation (late Gelasian–early Calabrian), reaching up to 300 m in thickness and deposited in a shallow-marine environment. This succession is characterized by three high-frequency transgressive–regressive sedimentary cycles, each 80–120 m thick. Transgressive phases are represented by inner shelf and coastal deposits, predominantly composed of clay, silt and fine sands, extending eastward from the basin centre toward the Apennine reliefs. These deposits alternate with thick gravelly–sandy progradational wedges, deposited during regressive phases and extending seaward up to 15 km, represented by coarse-grained river deltas fed mainly by conglomerate alluvial systems originating from the adjacent Rieti intermontane basin. The correlation between marine and continental deposits is further supported by the occurrence of rich mixed brackish–marine and freshwater molluscs and ostracod assemblages found in lignite-bearing marsh and lagoon deposits interbedded with the fluvio-deltaic sediments. Additional stratigraphic constraints are provided by foraminiferal markers (*Globorotalia inflata*–*Globorotalia cariacensis* biozones) and Upper Villafranchian mammalian faunas.

Coupling Terrestrial and Marine Proxies: Pollen and Dinocyst records from the Eastern Mediterranean toward the onset of the Quaternary

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The marine sedimentary sequence ODP U967, located south of Cyprus in the central Eastern Mediterranean Basin, occupies a key ecotonal position between African, Asian, and Mediterranean climatic domains, under the influence of multiple interacting atmospheric and oceanographic circulation systems. This exceptionally sensitive setting allows intercepting pollen from adjacent continental regions (Anatolia, the Syro-Palestinian margin, North Africa, and Cyprus) and marine circulation processes influencing aquatic biological assemblages. Thus, the same record captures the coupled signal of terrestrial vegetation dynamics and oceanographic variability.

Within the framework of the project “PPT Impact”, the present study pursues combines pollen and dinocyst analyses to explore their joint dynamics and common/divergent responses to climate variability during the Late Piacenzian (2.6-2.8 Ma), a key interval immediately preceding the onset of the Quaternary and the associated reorganization of climate-ocean systems.

Preliminary results revealed a climatically driven pattern of alternating sterile and non-sterile layers, which is consistent with cyclic orbital oscillations and provides additional constraints on sapropel formation in the eastern Mediterranean stratigraphic record. Furthermore, the direct comparison of these palaeoecological proxies with independent geochemical and palaeoclimatic evidence from the same sedimentary sequence allowed us to investigate critical thresholds in temperature and aeolian/fluviol inputs affecting the preservation of biological proxies.

The recorded pollen signal highlights the coexistence of deciduous and evergreen Mediterranean forest elements, along with extinct arboreal taxa, with relatively high percentages of xerophytic herbaceous taxa characteristic of steppe environments and semi-arid landscapes. The dinocyst assemblage reveals a dominance of warm-water and outer neritic taxa, together allowing the identification of cyclic warm oscillations consistent with interglacial conditions preceding the transition to the Quaternary.

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Contrasting fluvial morphodynamics of Alpine and Apennine systems (Northern Italy) under Quaternary forcing: implications for stratigraphic correlations

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Sedimentary dynamics and landscape evolution can be driven by glacial–interglacial oscillations, which can generate cyclic phases of erosion and deposition, producing stratigraphic frameworks that record environmental and geological variability over time. Among continental archives, fluvial systems are particularly significant for reconstructing such processes.

This study aims to elucidate the dynamic interactions and evolution of adjacent axial and transverse river systems through the analysis of Quaternary successions and geomorphic elements in a sector of the central Po Valley (Northern Italy). The Po Valley is shaped by rivers draining both the Alps and the Apennines, which converge into the Po River system.

A comprehensive geological dataset is being assembled through the integration of field-based mapping of geomorphological, sedimentological and palaeo-hydraulic features with shallow subsurface borehole data and remote sensing analyses. This approach allowed the identification of depositional units and the reconstruction of stratigraphic relationships and subsurface architecture. The chronostratigraphic framework was established based on radiometric dating and archaeological evidence, providing temporal constraints for stratigraphic correlation and palaeo-environmental reconstruction.

The results shed light on the role of the northward migration of the Po River in the postglacial fluvial evolution. The northern alpine tributaries are characterized by incision-dominated dynamics, driven by marked changes in hydraulic regime and sediment supply. By contrast, southern rivers draining Apennine catchments have built a postglacial unit dominated by aggradation, preserved as stacked palaeo-Po fluvial terrace geometries.

This asynchronous evolution provides a valuable framework for defining correlation strategies across Quaternary successions of the Po Basin and for comparing the observed post-15 ka evolution with traditional sequence stratigraphic models (LST–TST–HST transition) that are routinely applied for stratigraphic correlations.

Fossil land mammals stored at the Museo di Scienze della Terra (University of Bari): an example of Quaternary Apulian continental archives

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In the Apulian region (southern Italy), there is a large and valuable archive of Pleistocene land mammals. Fossil remains of this fauna have been found at various sites throughout Apulia, mainly represented by bone breccias, karst-fill deposits, and caves. Three different examples are presented here, differing in age, geographical position, and faunal composition: Pirro Nord (Gargano, northern Apulia; Early Pleistocene), Contrada Monticelli (Murge area, central Apulia; Middle Pleistocene), and Gagliano del Capo (Salento, southern Apulia; Late Pleistocene). Numerous remains from these sites are housed in the Museo di Scienze della Terra (University of Bari Aldo Moro). The Early Pleistocene fauna from the Pirro Nord site is conventionally dated to ~1.6–1.3 Ma. However, a numerical age significantly younger than previous estimates (~0.8 Ma) has recently been obtained using a multi-technique dating approach. The recent record of the spotted hyena, *Crocuta crocuta*, at Pirro Nord, a species that spread across Europe approximately 0.8 million years ago, appears consistent with this dating. These recent discoveries indicate the presence at Pirro Nord of younger deposits, probably dating to the early Middle Pleistocene. The Contrada Monticelli site is associated with the beginning of the Middle Pleistocene on the basis of its faunal assemblage and is correlated with the Isernia FU (0.6–0.55 Ma). It is one of the few Apulian sites dating to this specific interval, which was characterized by significant faunal turnover. Attempts at absolute dating using encrusting sediments and dental enamel from some of the site's finds are still underway. Several large, curved tusks and tusk fragments, attributed to the woolly mammoth *Mammuthus primigenius*, together with a skull of the woolly rhinoceros *Coelodonta antiquitatis*, were found at the Gagliano del Capo site. The so-called Mammuthus–Coelodonta faunal complex was widespread throughout the Italian Peninsula at the end of Marine Isotope Stage (MIS) 3 and during MIS 2, reaching southern Italy only during the last glaciation. Therefore, the Gagliano del Capo faunal assemblage can be chronologically attributed to MIS 2. The mammalian faunal archives preserved in Apulia provide important temporal windows into the Quaternary, significantly enhancing biochronological and palaeoenvironmental knowledge of this time interval.

River long-profile analysis in the Parco Regionale “Terra delle Gravine” (Southern Italy): try to correlate inherited base-levels with Quaternary marine terraces

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The Parco Regionale “Terra delle Gravine”, located in the northwestern sector of the Gulf of Taranto (southern Italy), hosts one of the largest networks of fluviokarst valleys (“gravine”) in the Mediterranean. The drainage basins incised into the Apulia foreland margin preserve significant evidence of Quaternary landscape evolution, driven by regional uplift, sea-level oscillations, tectonic activity, and lithological controls. This study investigates river long-profile analysis as a semi-quantitative method for reconstructing inherited fluvial base levels and assessing their correlation with Quaternary marine terraces in the park area. Geomorphometric analyses of the main drainage basins were integrated with χ -transformations of trunk-stream longitudinal profiles. High-resolution digital elevation models derived from regional topographic datasets were processed in a geographic information system and analysed using TopoToolbox routines in MATLAB. χ -plots, normalised channel steepness indices, and knickpoint distributions were used to identify relict equilibrium profiles, transient incision phases, and sectors affected by lithological or structural discontinuities. Reconstruction of paleo-long profiles enabled the recognition of inherited Quaternary base levels and their spatial correspondence with marine terrace remnants preserved along the Ionian margin. Preliminary results indicate that several drainage basins within the park share morphodynamic characteristics, including relict graded profiles associated with Middle–Upper Quaternary marine terraces, major slope-break and vertical-step knickpoints, and pronounced transitions between Plio–Pleistocene foredeep deposits and resistant Cretaceous carbonate bedrock. Although several knickpoints coincide with lithological boundaries, the variability in incision patterns across the gravine systems reflects the combined effects of Quaternary uplift, progressive base-level lowering, and litho-structural inheritance. The correlation between reconstructed fluvial base levels and marine terrace elevations suggests that the gravine systems preserve a geomorphic record of successive sea-level stillstands and regional uplift phases. Overall, the proposed approach provides a reproducible framework for investigating long-term landscape evolution and fluvial response to base-level changes in Mediterranean fluvial and fluviokarst environments.